

Study of Complexing Equilibria of Hafnium with Chrome Azurol S in Aqueous Solution

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Chrome Azurol S is proposed as a sensitive and selective chelating reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of hafnium. Chelate formation is a function of acid concentration of the solution. The chelates 1:1 and 1:2 (metal : ligand) exist simultaneously from pH 1.0 to 1.3. At pH 1.5 only 1:1 chelate is found to exist while at pH 2.0 and above, 2:1 (metal : ligand) chelate exists. At higher pH the chelate precipitates out due to the hydrolysis of hafnium. The stability of chelate, its composition and analytical applications are investigated. Certain masking reagents are also suggested for eliminating the effects of interfering metal ions, in the determination of hafnium with chrome Azurol S.

SODIUM salt of 3-sulpho-2,6-dichloro hydroxy dimethyl fuchsonic dicarboxylic acid, commonly known as Chrome Azurol S, (abbreviated as CAS, has been widely used as a chromogenic reagent for various metal ions. It has been extensively used in the spectrophotometric determination of many metals.¹⁻⁶ The nature and stability constants of various chelates of CAS with different metals have been reported by Dey and coworkers.⁷⁻⁹ Klausen and Langmyhr⁶ have studied different polynuclear complexes of Fe (III) with CAS. Very little work appears to have been done on the CAS complexes of tetravalent metal ions.¹⁰⁻¹² Recently a detailed investigation has been done on zirconium chelates of CAS in these laboratories.¹³

From the literature it appears that no work has been done on the chelates of hafnium with CAS. Thus the present communication describes, for the first time, the systematic study regarding the characteristics and analytical studies on the chelates of hafnium with CAS at different pH values.

Experimental

Apparatus: Beckman DU - 2 spectrophotometer along with glass cuvettes of 1 cm. thickness was used for noting the absorbance values. A pH meter manufactured by Trombay electronic instruments with glass and calomel electrodes was used for adjusting the pH of the solutions.

Reagents: Hafnium oxychloride (spectrographically standardized) supplied by Johnson Matthey, England, was used directly for making its solution in 2M perchloric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of hafnium.

CAS, supplied by Fluka, was purified by making its free acid and recrystallizing it three times from 50% ethanol. Its purity (99.8%) was checked by titrating it potentiometrically. Its solution was then prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity in sodium hydroxide solution. All other chemicals used were of A. R. grade.

Conditions of study: The standard solutions of CAS and of hafnium were always freshly prepared.

The range of final concentration of the solution was 10^{-5} to 10^{-6} M. The pH of the solutions was adjusted with NaOH and HClO₄ solutions. The mixtures were allowed to stand for at least half an hour for full development of colour. Red-violet coloured water soluble complexes were formed when the CAS was added to the metal ion solution of hafnium. No changes were observed if the order of addition of reagent was changed.

Results and Discussion

Acid dissociation constant of CAS: The acid dissociation of CAS may be represented as

Malat¹⁴ measured the dissociation constant of CAS by spectrophotometric methods and found pK values as 2.45, 4.86 and 11.47 respectively. We redetermined these constants using the spectrophotometric procedures described by Albert and Serjeant¹⁵ and obtained the values of pK₁, pK₂ and pK₃ as 2.5, 4.80 and 11.5 respectively. The -SO₃H group present might be dissociating at lower pH value and thus not permitting its determination under the present conditions of study.

Characteristics of the chelates: To find the nature and number of complexes formed, three series of solutions containing reagent : metal ratio (c'/c) as 4 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 4 were prepared. These solutions were adjusted to different pH values and their absorption spectra was noted in the entire visible range. The observations are summarised as below.

TABLE I—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF Hf: CAS CHELATE

Concentration of HfOCl₂·8H₂O = 5.0×10^{-5} M.
Concentration of CAS = 5.0×10^{-5} M.

Ratio	λ_{max} (nm) at pH						
reagent : metal	0.8	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5
1:0	470	470	470	470	470	470	480
4:1	470	470	480	490	490	500	500
1:1	470	550	550	550	530	530	530
1:4	470	550	550	550	550	550	550

The above observations are quite interesting and clearly show that no chelation occurs at pH 0.8 and below. At pH 1.0 formation of the chelate is inferred due to the shift in λ_{max} to 550 nm. It is to be mentioned here that in the ratio of 4:1 (ligand : metal), the λ_{max} shifts towards the λ_{max} of the ligand which is due to the domination of the reagent. The chelate exists between 1.0 to 3.5 pH with a decrease in stability after pH 2.5. This is because of the preferred hydrolysis of hafnium. A slight change in λ_{max} to 530 nm in 1:1 ratio may be due to the above reason. The dominance of the reagent is again marked in 4:1 ratio at these pH values.

Due to the presence of various λ_{max} s at different pH values in different ratios, it was difficult to conclude the number of complexes formed in this case. In order to establish the different complexes, the composition of the chelate was determined by the methods of Job's and Mole ratio at all the above pH values, i. e., from 1.0 to 3.5 at 480, 490, 530 and 550 nm. It was found that at 500 nm and below the complex has a negative absorbance than that of the ligand alone and the results were erratic. The studies at 530 and 550 nm, however, gave interesting results. It was found that CAS forms 1:1 complex from pH 1.0 to 1.5 (Fig. 1, at pH 1.5 curve A). It may be observed from the fig. that there is a weak but significant peak corresponding to 1:2 (metal : ligand) complex (fig. 1, curve B) at pH 1.0. However, this weak peak vanishes at pH 1.5, showing the existence of only one, 1:1 complex at pH 1.5, having λ_{max} 550 nm. On increasing the pH further it was observed that from pH 2.0 to 3.5 a second complex exists having the same λ_{max} , 550 nm, but different composition corresponding to 2:1 (metal : ligand) complex (Fig. 1, curve C). This complex, however, was stable only upto 2.5 pH and there after becomes unstable due to hydrolysis of hafnium.

Fig. 1. : Composition of hafnium-CAS chelates: Concentration of $HfOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ and CAS = $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, Curve A = pH 1.5, Curve B = pH 1.0 and Curve C = pH 2.0.

These studies were confirmed at 530 nm also showing the existence of above complexes. Further study of these two complexes was done at 1.5 pH (for 1:1 complex) and at 2.0 pH (for 2:1 complex) at 550 nm.

Study of Equilibrium of Hf-CAS Chelate: 1:1 complex of Hf with CAS at pH 1.5 forms almost instantaneously. It has been found that this complex is anionic in nature as it was completely adsorbed on ion exchange resin Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The reagent exists as H_3CAS^- at this pH according to the study of the dissociation constant of the ligand. This has two positions for chelation

- (1) through -COOH group and adjacent phenolic group and,
- (2) through -COOH group and adjacent quinonide group.

Chelation through first position will liberate two protons from the H_3CAS^- whereas the complexation through the second position will liberate only one proton. The studies on the number of protons liberated could not be made due to a very short range of pH within which the chelate is stable.

The data reported on the hydrolysis of hafnium suggests the hydrolysed species, $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$ and $[Hf(OH)_2]^{2+}$ occurring at this pH range. Consideration of the various complexing equilibria involved by assuming the reacting species of hafnium to be Hf^{4+} and $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$, forming complex with H_3CAS^- , with both the chelating possibilities, suggest the complex to be cationic or neutral in nature which is against the experimental observations (chelate being anionic). The complexing equilibria involved with $[Hf(OH)_2]^{2+}$ as reacting species is given below.

The first equilibria, showing the complexation through the first position yields anionic complex, whereas through the second position, it is neutral. Thus it may be concluded that the reacting species for the 1:1 complex is $[Hf(OH)_2]^{2+}$. It may be possible to consider the reacting species to be $[Hf(OH)_3]^+$, but as the concentration of this is less at the pH 1.5, the reaction should have been a slow one. It is, however, a fast reaction as reported earlier.

The formation of 2:1 (metal : ligand) complex at pH 2.0 is comparatively a slower reaction. Here the reacting species can not be taken as Hf^{4+} , $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$ and $[Hf(OH)_2]^{2+}$ as in all these cases, the equilibrium will be slow and the resulting complex will be cationic or neutral. This complex is also completely adsorbed on Ion Exchange resin Amberlite IR-45, showing its anionic nature. Hence, it is only $[Hf(OH)_3]^+$ which can be taken as reacting species to give an anionic complex. The equilibrium is shown below,

It may be noted, here, that the reaction is comparatively slower than the first complex showing that it is only $[Hf(OH)_3]^+$ which is forming 2:1 complex. This

complex, however, is less stable and precipitates out after keeping the solution overnight. It was thus not possible to calculate its conditional stability constant. The conditional stability constant for the first complex (1:1) has been calculated by the method of Anderson and co-workers^{1,6} modified by Dey and co-workers¹⁷. The value is found to be 1.54×10^5 . The structure of both the complexes may be assigned as below.

Analytical aspects of the system

2:1 complex at pH 2.0 is not suitable for analytical studies as the stability of the chelate is not much. It is, however, seen that the 1:1 complex at pH 1.5 is quite stable and sensitive. Thus it was studied at pH 1.5 and 550 nm. The chelate is found to be stable upto 50°. The maximum colour intensity is obtained when the reagent is present in four fold excess than the metal concentration.

Fig. 2. : Ringbom plot to determine the effective photometric concentration range at pH 1.5. Concentration of hafnium = 0.5 to 7.1 ppm. $\lambda_{max} = 550$ nm.

Range for Beer's law and photometric determination : It was observed that Beer's law holds good in the range of concentration of hafnium from 0.5 to 7.1 ppm. To evaluate optimum range and analytical accuracy, Ringbom's curve¹⁸ was drawn by plotting % transmittance as ordinate against log concentration of hafnium as abscissa (fig. 2), Thus the range as derived by the maximum slope of the curve was 1.6 to 5.0 ppm of hafnium.

Molar Extinction Coefficient and sensitivity of the complex : The molar extinction coefficient of the complex was determined by taking a constant amount of metal ion and different amounts of excess of CAS at 1.5 pH. The absorbance was noted at 550 nm. The molar extinction coefficient and sensitivity of the Hf - CAS complex was found to be 31,500 and 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (in Sandell's unit) respectively.

Effect of diverse ions : For studying the effects of diverse ions a difference of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as an interference. The ions which have been found to seriously interfere in the determination of Hf with CAS are sulphate, phosphate, fluoride, oxalate, tartrate, citrate, copper, chromium, gallium, iron, indium, thorium, titanium, zirconium and uranium. Tolerance limit of other ions are as shown below. The ions which do not interfere in the system at all concentrations are Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , ClO_4^- , SCN^- , CH_3COO^- , NH_4^+ , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , and Tl^{3+} .

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Ions	added as	Max. tolerance limit
La ³⁺	La(NO ₃) ₃	540
Y ³⁺	YCl ₃	356
Co ²⁺	Co(NO ₃) ₂	236
Ni ²⁺	Ni(NO ₃) ₂	254
V ⁵⁺	NH ₄ VO ₃	20

Masking of the interfering cations : Hafnium is mostly present along with zirconium. Thorium, titanium, iron and uranium are also associated with hafnium in varying amounts in certain ores. These metals are found to interfere seriously in the determina-

tion of hafnium with CAS, at pH 1.5. Therefore, a very large number of masking reagents were tried in order to eliminate the interference of Th^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} and Cr^{3+} . It has been found that these can be masked with certain reagents as shown below.

TABLE 3—MASKING OF THE INTERFERING CATIONS.

Metal ions	Masking reagents 1 ml of 0.05% aqueous solution
Th^{4+}	2,6-dihydroxybenzoic acid.
Ti^{4+}	Thiourea, Aspartic acid, 2,6-dihydroxybenzoic acid.
Cr^{3+}	Hydroxyquinone, 2-picolinic acid.
Fe^{2+}	Sulfosalicylic acid, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid.
Fe^{3+}	Sym-diphenylcarbazine, Gallic acid.
UO_2^{2+}	Sulfosalicylic acid, Thiourea.

It may be mentioned, here, that thorium if present in excess can not be masked with 2,6-dihydroxybenzoic acid and it interferes seriously. It is clear that Zr^{4+} interferes at all concentrations. It may, however, be separated from hafnium by ion exchange methods¹⁹. Care is to be taken that when all these interfering ions are present together then masking reagent for one might interfere for the other.

Precision of colour reactions: The absorbance readings showed average and relative standard deviation values as 0.07 and 2.39% for hafnium respectively.

Recommended procedure: To a moderately acidic metal ion solution containing 1.6 to 5.0 ppm hafnium, add about four fold excess of CAS solution. Adjust pH to 1.5. Allow the mixtures to stand for half an hour for equilibration and then measure absorbance at 550 nm. The absorbance value of an unknown sample solution can then be compared with the calibration curve obtained earlier and the concentration of the unknown sample can, thus, be determined.

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